

**USER SATISFACTION ON INFORMATION COMMUNICATION
TECHNOLOGY- BASED INFORMATION RESOURCES AND SERVICES
AMONG THE FACULTY MEMBERS OF ENGINEERING COLLEGES IN
PUDUCHERRY AND KARAIKAL DISTRICTS**

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the level of satisfaction among faculty members with information resources and services through ICT-enabled engineering college libraries in the Puducherry and Karaikal districts. The objective of the study is to assess the efficacy, accessibility, and availability of ICT-based resources such as online databases, e-books, e-journals, institutional repositories, and digital library services. For data collection, a systematic questionnaire was administered to faculty members. Appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data. The results indicate that most faculty members use ICT-based resources in their academic, research, and instructional activities. Additionally, the report emphasizes patrons' satisfaction with library support services, the availability of electronic resources, and access speed. However, the report identified certain difficulties, such as the need to provide training for patrons and the inaccessibility of certain databases. To effectively utilize ICT-based library services, the research suggests that ICT infrastructure, e-resources, and user awareness campaigns need improvement.

KEY WORDS

Accessibility, Digital Library Service, Information Resource, Patrons' Satisfaction, Digital Repositories.

1. INTRODUCTION

Significant changes have occurred in the functioning of academic libraries, especially in engineering institutions, through the application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The term ICT is defined as the integration of computer technologies and communication networks that facilitate the collection, storage, processing, retrieval, and dissemination of information in digital formats. The application of ICT in the functioning of libraries has facilitated the development of information systems that have enhanced the efficiency of information delivery and user access.

1.1. USE OF ICT INFORMATION RESOURCES

Engineering college libraries are making significant use of ICT information resources such as e-journals, e-books, e-databases, e-theses, digital repositories, and full-text databases to support the academic and research activities of the students and faculty members. In addition, various ICT facilities such as Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), Current Awareness Services (CAS), Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI), digital resource centers, bibliographic services, and online journal laboratories enable the users to access the required information efficiently and effectively. These facilities play a vital role in supporting the faculty members in

accessing the required information in digital formats that is required for research publication, teaching, and academic development.

1.2. USER GROUPS:

One of the main user groups in the Engineering colleges is the faculty members, and the level of satisfaction they enjoy with the ICT facilities and services is an important aspect that can be taken as an indication of the successful implementation of the library information systems. The assessment of user satisfaction is helpful to understand the usability and quality of the services offered by the library. The analysis of the users' opinions about the support staff, the availability of e-resources, and the efficiency of the ICT facilities is helpful to improve the performance and management of the library resources.

In the present study, special attention is focused on the opinions of faculty members regarding the assistance provided by library staff in accessing digital information resources, their level of satisfaction with different categories of electronic resources, and their opinions regarding ICT-based library services. Also, the statistical differences in their levels of satisfaction are analyzed using appropriate methods. Understanding these aspects will help the engineering college libraries in Puducherry and Karaikal districts develop their ICT infrastructure, improve their collections of electronic resources, and offer better services to faculty members in meeting their growing needs for information resources.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Endouware and Omehia (2022) surveyed 72 librarians across four universities to assess their ICT competencies. Using a five-point Likert scale, the study found librarians proficient in basic word processing, data storage, internet use, and electronic services, but lacking skills in operating systems and software. The authors recommended in-house training, increased awareness, and modern ICT tools to improve digital service delivery.

Ahmed and Rehman (2016) examined the capacity and training needs of professional librarians working in public universities. The study revealed that the level of ICT skills remained inadequate, mainly due to reliance on self-learning and insufficient staffing, and recommended systematic capacity-building efforts to enhance professional capabilities.

Shahzad and Khan (2022) study on integrated semantic digital library (SDL) adoption identified five key challenges: interoperability, model creation, language diversity, lack of skilled personnel, and technical issues. These challenges hinder SDLs' ability to provide crucial context-based information resources due to complexities in areas like ontologies and interoperability.

Haneefa, Madhu, and Ashok (2014) carried out a study to assess the level of ICT proficiency among Library and Information Science (LIS) students in universities. The findings indicated that the usage of electronic databases and content management software was relatively low. The study highlighted the need for structured training

programs to enhance students' ICT skills, enabling them to make better use of available library resources.

3. OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate the attitude of library staff towards access support to respondents.
- To evaluate the usage of ICT products and services by faculty members.
- To evaluate the satisfaction level of ICT-based library services among faculty members.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design to examine the attitude of library staff and satisfaction with ICT-enabled library resources among faculty members of Engineering Colleges in Puducherry and Karaikal.

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale. A total of 1,186 valid responses were obtained from faculty members across 14 Engineering Institutions.

The collected data were analyzed using percentage analysis, mean and standard deviation, ranking method, and ANOVA Test

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 5.1: User Opinion on Library Staff Attitude Toward Access Support by Respondents

S. No	User Opinion	Frequency	Percent
1	They take personal interest and are polite and courteous in facilitating access	359	30.3
2	Demonstrate and teach how to use information resources	328	27.7
3	They are well-trained in accessing information resources and up to date in their knowledge	214	18
4	Library staff efficiently select databases and use relevant search terms to retrieve accurate references.	187	15.8
5	They provide prompt assistance and follow-up to ensure users successfully access the required information	98	8.3
Total		1186	100

The analysis of Table 5.1 depicts that the majority of respondents, 359 (30.3), expressed that library staff take personal interest and are polite and courteous in facilitating access. This was followed by 328 (27.7) respondents who indicated that staff demonstrate and teach how to use information resources. Further, 214 (18) of respondents stated that the staff are well-trained in accessing information resources and up to date in their knowledge, while 187 (15.8) respondents highlighted that the staff efficiently select databases and use relevant search terms to retrieve accurate references. Only 98 (8.3) of respondents mentioned that staff provide prompt assistance and follow-up to ensure successful access to the required information. It is found that more than 30% of the users expressed that the library staff takes a personal interest in providing information to users.

Table 5.2: Satisfaction with the Collection of E-Resources by Respondents

S. No	Satisfaction level	VDS	DS	N	S	VS	Total	M	SD	R
1	CDs / DVD-ROM Resources	158 (13.3)	154 (13.0)	308 (26.0)	308 (26.0)	258 (21.8)	1186 (100.0)	3.2985	1.30573	7
2	E-Database	180 (15.2)	171 (14.4)	193 (16.3)	251 (21.2)	391 (33.0)	1186 (100.0)	3.4233	1.4506	5
3	E-Journals	92 (7.8)	127 (10.7)	253 (21.3)	343 (28.9)	371 (31.3)	1186 (100.0)	3.6526	1.23824	2
4	E-Reports	139 (11.7)	141 (11.9)	261 (22.0)	366 (30.9)	279 (23.5)	1186 (100.0)	3.4258	1.28738	4
5	E-Content pages	156 (13.2)	135 (11.4)	163 (13.7)	274 (23.1)	458 (38.6)	1186 (100.0)	3.6265	1.423	3
6	E-Clippings	183 (15.4)	174 (14.7)	260 (21.9)	190 (16.0)	379 (32.0)	1186 (100.0)	3.344	1.44422	6
7	E-Books	235 (19.8)	221 (18.6)	195 (16.4)	188 (15.9)	347 (29.3)	1186 (100.0)	3.161	1.51121	8
8	E-Thesis and Dissertation	287 (24.2)	291 (24.5)	226 (19.1)	198 (16.7)	184 (15.5)	1186 (100.0)	2.7479	1.39245	11
9	E-Bibliographic databases	197 (16.6)	264 (22.3)	224 (18.9)	175 (14.8)	326 (27.5)	1186 (100.0)	3.1425	1.45449	9
10	E-Learning Resources (ppt, word, pdf files)	203 (17.1)	389 (32.8)	150 (12.6)	139 (11.7)	305 (25.7)	1186 (100.0)	2.9612	1.4693	10
11	E-Full Text Databases	89 (7.5)	161 (13.6)	225 (19.0)	188 (15.9)	523 (44.1)	1186 (100.0)	3.7546	1.33805	1

Source: Primary Data 5-VS – Very Satisfied 4-S – Satisfied 3-N – Neutral 2-DS – Dissatisfied 1-VDS – Very Dissatisfied

The above table 5.2 describes the satisfaction of respondents towards the collection of e-resources with their respective ranking. It is observed that eleven parameters such as CDs/DVD-ROM Resources, E-Database, E-Journals, E-Reports, E-Content Pages, E-Clippings, E-Books, E-Thesis and Dissertation, E-Bibliographic Databases, E-Learning Resources (ppt, word, pdf files), and E-Full Text Databases were evaluated. The first rank was given to E-Full Text Databases with a mean value of 3.7546, followed by the second rank for E-Journals with a mean value of 3.6526,

and the third rank for E-Content Pages with a mean value of 3.6265. The fourth rank was awarded to E-Reports (M = 3.4258), fifth to E-Database (M = 3.4233), sixth to E-Clippings (M = 3.3440), seventh to CDs/DVD-ROM Resources (M = 3.2985), eighth to E-Books (M = 3.1610), ninth to E-Bibliographic Databases (M = 3.1425), tenth to E-Learning Resources (M = 2.9612), and remaining eleventh rank was given to E-Thesis and Dissertation with the lowest mean value of 2.7479 respectively.

Respondents are most satisfied with E-Full Text Databases, E-Journals, and E-Content Pages, while satisfaction with E-Thesis and Dissertation was the lowest, indicating the need for improvement in this area.

it indicates that most of them are satisfied with the e-full-text database, e-learning resources, and e-theses and dissertations.

S. No	Satisfaction level	VDS	DS	N	S	VS	Total	M	SD	R
1	Current awareness services (CAS)	78 (6.6)	153 (12.9)	231 (19.5)	384 (32.4)	340 (28.7)	1186 (100.0)	3.6872	1.70602	1
2	Reference services	197 (16.6)	190 (16.0)	325 (27.4)	161 (13.6)	313 (26.4)	1186 (100.0)	3.1712	1.41011	6
3	Digital resource centre (DRC)	177 (14.9)	125 (10.5)	236 (19.9)	265 (22.3)	383 (32.3)	1186 (100.0)	3.4654	1.41513	3
4	Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI) Services:	253 (21.3)	337 (28.4)	131 (11.0)	183 (15.4)	282 (23.8)	1186 (100.0)	2.9191	1.49605	9
5	Circulation services	103 (8.7)	271 (22.8)	193 (16.3)	160 (13.5)	459 (38.7)	1186 (100.0)	3.5067	1.41554	2
6	Online public access catalogue (OPAC)	300 (25.3)	120 (10.1)	147 (12.4)	152 (12.8)	467 (39.4)	1186 (100.0)	3.3086	1.65023	5
7	Online journal lab	259 (21.8)	235 (19.8)	154 (13.0)	195 (16.4)	343 (28.9)	1186 (100.0)	3.1079	1.54379	7
8	Bibliographic Service	193 (16.3)	144 (12.1)	233 (19.6)	263 (22.2)	353 (29.8)	1186 (100.0)	3.3702	1.43156	4
9	Database Search Guide	194 (16.4)	338 (28.5)	138 (11.6)	250 (21.1)	266 (22.4)	1186 (100.0)	3.0472	1.43063	8

Table 5.3 Satisfaction level of ICT product library services by Respondents

Source: Primary Data 5-VS – Very Satisfied 4-S – Satisfied 3-N – Neutral 2-DS – Dissatisfied 1-VDS – Very Dissatisfied

Table 5.3 and attempt to identify the satisfaction level of ICT product library services as ranked by respondents. The users assigned the first rank for Current Awareness Services (CAS) with a mean value (3.6872), followed by the second rank for Circulation Services with a mean value (3.5067), third rank for Digital Resource Centre (DRC) with a mean value (3.4654), fourth rank for Bibliographic Service with a mean value (3.3702), fifth rank for Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) with a mean value (3.3086), sixth rank for Reference Services with a mean value (3.1712), seventh rank for Online Journal Lab with a mean value (3.1079), eighth rank for Database Search Guide with a mean value (3.0472), and the ninth rank was given to Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI) Services with the

lowest mean value (2.9191) by respondents. It is found that most of the users' satisfaction levels with the ICT Products and services occupy first position

Table 5.4: ANOVA Test of Satisfaction level of ICT product library services

S. No	Satisfaction level of ICT product library services		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Current awareness services (CAS)	Between Groups	22.772	2	11.386	7.897	0.000
		Within Groups	1705.6	1183	1.442		
		Total	1728.372	1185			
2	Reference services	Between Groups	36.107	2	18.053	9.205	0.000
		Within Groups	2320.147	1183	1.961		
		Total	2356.254	1185			
3	Digital resource centre (DRC)	Between Groups	22.902	2	11.451	5.764	0.003
		Within Groups	2350.18	1183	1.987		
		Total	2373.083	1185			
4	Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI) Services:	Between Groups	23.644	2	11.822	5.321	0.005
		Within Groups	2628.585	1183	2.222		
		Total	2652.229	1185			
5	Circulation services	Between Groups	100.488	2	50.244	26.139	0.000
		Within Groups	2273.958	1183	1.922		
		Total	2374.446	1185			
6	Online public access catalogue (OPAC)	Between Groups	260.759	2	130.38	51.997	0.000
		Within Groups	2966.293	1183	2.507		
		Total	3227.052	1185			
7	Online journal lab	Between Groups	45.796	2	22.898	9.75	0.000
		Within Groups	2778.389	1183	2.349		
		Total	2824.185	1185			
8	Bibliographic Service	Between Groups	25.004	2	12.502	6.153	0.002
		Within Groups	2403.5	1183	2.032		
		Total	2428.503	1185			
9	Database Search Guide	Between Groups	49.979	2	24.99	12.446	0.000
		Within Groups	2375.376	1183	2.008		
		Total	2425.356	1185			

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.4 the ANOVA test results revealed statistically significant differences in respondents' satisfaction with ICT-based library services across all nine parameters examined CAS ($F=7.897$, $p=0.000$), reference services ($F=9.205$, $p=0.000$), digital resource centre ($F=5.764$, $p=0.003$), SDI services ($F=5.321$, $p=0.005$), circulation services ($F=26.139$, $p=0.000$), OPAC ($F=51.997$, $p=0.000$), online journal lab ($F=9.750$, $p=0.000$), bibliographic service ($F=6.153$, $p=0.002$), and database search guide ($F=12.446$, $p=0.000$). Since the p-values are less than 0.05 in all cases, the null hypotheses were rejected, confirming significant variation in satisfaction levels among respondents. This implies that while some ICT services were well-received, others require targeted improvement to ensure uniform user satisfaction and optimized service quality. It is found that the user's satisfaction level is uniform and also optimized service quality.

Table 5.5: Rating of ICT-Based Library Services in Engineering Colleges by Respondents

S. No	Rating	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
1	Poor	88	7.4	7.4
2	Fair	40	3.4	3.4
3	Good	88	7.4	7.4
4	Very good	432	36.4	36.4
5	Excellent	538	45.4	45.4
Total		1186	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.5 shows the respondents' rating of ICT-based library services in engineering colleges. Out of 1,186 responses, 88 (7.4) per cent rated the services as poor, 40 (3.4) per cent rated them as fair, and 88 (7.4) per cent rated them as good. A larger group of 432 (36.4) per

cent rated the services as very good, while the majority of 538 (45.4) per cent rated them as excellent.

The results indicate that more than 45% respondents rated the ICT-based library services positively, with excellent and very

FINDINGS

- Based on the user opinion, more than 30% of the users expressed that library staff takes a personal interest in providing information to users.
- It is found that most of them are satisfied with the E-Full database, e-learning resources, and e-theses and dissertations.
- Based on the satisfaction with the facilities available in the library, ICT products and services are more satisfied
- It is evident that the users' satisfaction level is uniform when using ICT products and services.
- The findings of the study show that more than 45% of the respondents rated the ICT-based library service positively

CONCLUSION

The study aims to identify the level of satisfaction of the faculty members regarding the information resources and services based on ICT facilities in engineering college libraries of Puducherry and Karaikal districts. The findings of this study show that the facilities of ICT have improved information access and increased the efficiency of the information resources of the libraries to a great extent, as most of the respondents showed positive opinions regarding the support of the library staff, which indicates that the staff are polite, helpful, and assist the users in utilizing the information resources effectively.

Regarding the availability of information resources, the study found that the highest level of satisfaction was received by E-Full Text Databases, followed by the top rank, then E-Journals.

As far as ICT-based library services are concerned, the results showed that Current Awareness Services (CAS) was ranked highest in terms of satisfaction. The results of ANOVA also confirmed that there were significant differences in satisfaction levels.

Overall, it may be concluded that most of the library users rated library services in terms of ICT as very good or excellent, reflecting high user satisfaction with library services. The study also recommends that ICT facilities should be improved, e-resources should be increased, and user training programmes should be organized to improve the use of digital library services.

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